

11. EU Agroforestry Policy: an overview

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EURAF is an NGO, established in Paris on 16/11/2012, with a French Registration number of [W343014937](#), and a Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](#). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

- The EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)** is drafted by the Commission, and revised by both Parliament and the Council of Agricultural Ministers. Consensus is then negotiated between the three bodies. The new CAP (from 2023 onwards) has [just been agreed](#) in triologue. Parliament [increased the mentions of agroforestry](#) in the EU Strategic Plan Regulation from 3 to 18, but most of these were removed in triologue.
- The EU, via its [Climate Law](#), is now committed to a 55% reduction in emissions by 2030 compared to 1990, and neutrality by 2050. This includes AFOLU/LULUCF in national targets and greater opportunity for offsetting between sectors and countries. Details of a “Fit for 55 Package” [will be published on 14/7/21](#), including revision of the LULUCF Regulation and the Emissions Sharing Regulation and Emissions Trading Scheme. Carbon farming proposals are due by December 21.
- AF Definitions are given in:** a) **EU Regulation 1305/2013** ... “*Agroforestry is a land use system in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land*”, and b) **EURAF Constitution** .. “*Agroforestry practices include all forms of association of trees and crops (silvopastoral systems) and/or animals (silvopastoral systems) on a parcel of agricultural land, whether in the interior of the parcel or on its edges*”.
- An **Agroforestry Typology** is proposed by EURAF for use in farmers annual IACS/LPIS returns. It uses the existing CAP classification of parcels into a) forest or agriculture and b) arable or grassland or permanent-crops (e.g. olives, fruit trees, cork oak).
- Agroforestry is stressed in the **EU Green Deal**, the **Farm to Fork Strategy** and the **Biodiversity Strategy**. The last includes a commitment to 3 billion additional trees to be planted by 2030. EURAF is pushing for these to be Trees Outside Forests - to have the greatest environmental and climate impact.
- EU Member States (27) have 160 Mha of Forest and **21 Mha of Other Wooded Land (OWL)** and **9.15 Mha of Other Land with Tree Cover (OLTC)**, using FAO definitions. Adding OWL and OLTC together gives 15.9% of EU tree cover being “Trees Outside Forests” ([EURAF 2020a](#))- but this only includes blocks bigger than 0.5ha, and means that “**Trees outside Trees Outside Forests**” **must be considered!!** **The best estimate of agroforestry in the EU¹ is about 15.4 Mha** which is equivalent to about 3.6% of the territorial area and 8.8% of the utilised agricultural area ([den Herder et al 2017](#)).
- The **1998 EU Forest Strategy** contained 4 mentions of agroforestry. This shrank to one in the **2013 Strategy** and one in the leaked **2021 Strategy**. Agroforestry has never been mentioned in the Implementation Plans or reviews of these strategies.

Tree location	Agroforestry System	Agroforestry Practice	
		Agricultural Land	Forest Land
Trees inside parcels	Silvopastoral agroforestry	1 Wood pasture	9 Forest grazing
	Silvoarable agroforestry	2 Tree alley cropping 3 Coppice alley cropping 4 Multi-layer tree-gardens	10 Multi-layer tree gardens
	Permanent crop agroforestry	5 Orchard intercropping, 6 Orchard grazing.	
	Agro-silvo-pasture	7 Alternating cropping and grazing	
Trees between parcels	Tree Landscape Features (protected by CAP Conditionality Rules)	8 Tree-Landscape-Features : (protected hedges, scattered individual trees, trees in line, small groups of trees)	
Trees in settlements	Urban agroforestry	homegardens, allotments, etc.	

¹ Including the UK but excluding Croatia.

8. Eleven “**Good Agricultural and Environmental Practice (GAEC)**” rules must be followed by all farmers. GAEC9 includes conservation of Landscape Features (including individual trees, lines of trees, groups of trees if these are “declared” by Member States, and a minimum percent of “non productive areas” for arable land . New rules mean that Member States will have to record trees in these “non productive” areas as well as “hectares of agroforestry” by 2023. Data is stored in national/regional “**Land Parcel Identification Systems**” (pixel resolution of 0.5m) which all farmers edit annually. Each farmer must maintain 4% of non productive areas (including fallow and tree landscape features) or a total of 3% non productive areas + 4% of permitted productive features - including catch crops, cover crops, N-fixing crops and “hectares of agroforestry”.
9. **Ecoschemes** must be implemented by MS from 2023, and agroforestry and carbon farming are included. 20% (2022-24), rising to 25% (2025 onward) of the **CAP Pillar I budget** (€168.5 billion on targeted income support in 2021) must be spent on these. These are optional for farmers. Pillar I Ecoschemes go beyond the climate and environment commitments in GAEC rules.
10. The **CAP Pillar II budget** (€15.3 billion on rural development in 2021) includes spending on forest productive investments (submeasure 8.1 - afforestation, 8.2 - agroforestry establishment and management), forest protective investments (submeasures 8.3 and 8.4 - can include AF on forest land for fire protection), agri-environment-climate (submeasure 10.1) could include AF but no data is available. By the end of 2019 only 6 countries (PT, ES, IT, FR, BE, UK) and 30 regions (out of 118) have implemented submeasure 8.2, with planned hectares reduced from 84k (2015) to 60k (2019), and planned expenditure reduced from 130M€ (2015) to 64M€. (2019) By the end of 2019 only €3.3M had been spent ([Szedlak 2021](#)). Implementation has been poor because of a) lack of information for farmers/land managers, lack of information for management authorities, changing rules, confused announcements, competition from other measures (agri-environment, afforestation), low payment levels or periods.
11. Member States are consulting on their **CAP Strategic Plans** and must submit these to Brussels by the end of 2021. So far, the joint EU/Member State “Recommendations on CAP Strategic Plans” (December 2020) are disappointing since 16 recommendations make no mention of agroforestry.

AT	BE	BG	HR	CY	CZ	DK	EE	FI	FR	DE	GR	HU	IR	IT	LV	LT	LU	MT	NL	PL	PT	RO	SK	SI	ES	SE	
0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	4	1	6	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	6	1	0	0	2	0	27

12. The new CAP budget (2023-2028) is €270 billion, and at least 35% of the rural development funds (CAP Pillar II) will have to be devoted to agri-environment commitments “**which promote environmental, climate and animal welfare practices**”. However the [EU Court of Auditors](#) strongly criticised the current CAP for supposedly being “50% devoted to climate policies” yet having **zero effect on emissions** from agriculture. It criticises Member States for not investing in measures like afforestation and agroforestation, which would genuinely contribute to emissions mitigation.

13. Which means that “Impact Indicators” and “Result Indicators” used in the “**Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework**” ([European Commission 2021](#)) to measure the effectiveness of the CAP, must truly monitor the impact on the environment and climate **directly caused** by specific policy measures and submeasures. This is a huge challenge, and the indicators currently proposed by the EU are totally inadequate ([EURAF 2020b](#)).

	Member State	Crown Cover (%)	Minimum area (ha)	Tree Height (m)	Minimum width (m)
1	Croatia, Poland	10	0.1	2	10m Poland
2	Bulgaria, Germany	10	0.1	5	
3	Romania, Finland (south)	10	0.25	5	20m
4	Italy, Luxemburg	10	0.5	5	
5	Denmark, Finland (north), Sweden	10	0.5	5	20m , (10m Sweden)
6	Portugal	10	1	5	20
7	Ireland, Latvia	20	0.1	5	20
8	United Kingdom	20	0.1	2	20
9	Slovakia	20	0.3	5	
10	Belgium, Netherlands	20	0.5	5	30m Netherlands
11	Spain	20	1	3	25
12	Greece	25	0.3	2	
13	Lithuania	30	0.1	5	10
14	Slovenia	30	0.25	2	
15	Czech Republic, Estonia	30	0.5	2	20m Czech Republic
16	Hungary	30	0.5	5	10
17	Austria	30	0.05	2	10

14. Opportunities for **carbon farming in Europe** were investigated by the EU Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG-CLIMA), including a series of workshops and a technical handbook ([DG-CLIMA 2021](#)). Agroforestry and conservation of organic soils were recognised as the two front-running measures. EURAF gave a presentation at the final conference titled [Agroforestry for Carbon Farming](#).

15. Member States must report annually on **Greenhouse Gas emissions** to the UN Framework Convention for Climate change, and the Commission encourages them to use IPCC “Tier 3” and “Approach 3” methodology. The latter involves wall to wall identification of land use, and gives an opportunity for the national AFOLU/LPIS calculations to include the impact of trees on grassland and cropland, as well as in forests. National definitions of the **thresholds for forest land** are increasingly important, and are given in the [LULUCF Regulation](#). Any tree blocks which are smaller than the forest threshold must, in IPCC methodology, be reported as part of cropland or grassland ([EURAF 2020c](#)).
16. EURAF has published the following series of **Agroforestry Policy Briefings**. We are anxious to hear of good policy initiatives in North America which can be suggested to Member States for inclusion in their CAP Strategic Plans. More details of EURAF’s activities are available on our [website](#).
17. The Policy Priorities for Agroforestry were discussed at a Policy Webinar on [16-19 November 2020](#) and at the recent 5th European Agroforestry Conference “Agroforestry for the transition towards sustainability and bioeconomy” ([17-19 May 2021](#)). The 15 Policy Recommendations which EURAF has lobbied on are shown in the following box.

Box 1 - Recommendations from EURAF Agroforestry Policy Briefings 1 - 8 (MS means Member State)

1. The existing definition of agroforestry (AF) in the Rural Development Regulation (“a land use system in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land”) should not be changed, but should be clarified to make clear that trees can be inside parcels or on parcel-boundaries.
2. Eight possible agroforestry IACS/LPIS codes are suggested as part of the “EFA Layer” of the IACS/LPIS - related to “non-productive areas” (i.e. GAEC-9).
3. The IACS/LPIS codes for “Landscape Features” include individual trees, lines of trees and groups of trees. Powerful earth observation tools exist to identify these, and all MS should ensure that they are fully mapped in their LPIS system by 2023. They should count towards GAEC-9 and be fully eligible for Basic Payments.
4. The role of Trees outside the Forest should be explicitly recognised in the new Forest Strategy, and “agroforestation” should match existing planned “afforestation” at around 300,000,000 trees per year.
5. MS should implement the Commission’s [Working Paper](#) on direct payments: which says that Member States have the leeway to ensure agricultural area under agroforestry is “fully eligible for Basic Payments when justified based on the local specificities (e.g. density/species/size of the trees and pedo-climatic conditions) and the value added of the presence of trees to ensure sustainable agricultural use of the land”.
6. MS should recognise the potential for agroforestry to contribute to all ten Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC), and mention agroforestry accordingly in their GAEC guidance rules to farmers.
7. Agroforestry within agricultural parcels (called “hectares of agroforestry” in the current CAP) should be included in GAEC-9 areas, irrespective of whether it has been assisted by current or previous Pillar II schemes. This should apply to agroforestry on cropland, grassland and permanent crop areas.
8. Proposals have been made for five Pillar I Agroforestry and Landscape Feature Ecoschemes, which can be undertaken on a sequential annual basis, including planning, establishment and maintenance of existing areas like dehesa, parkland, wood pasture.
9. MS should include Pillar II “Establishment, Regeneration or Renovation of Agroforestry Systems” (aka submeasure 8.2) in their Strategic Plans as the primary way to establish new agroforestry areas and to enhance existing agroforestry like dehesa and wood pasture.
10. MS should include Pillar II “Forest Grazing” as part of the “Forest Protective Infrastructure” (aka sub-measures 8.3 and 8.4) in their Strategic Plans, as a potent means of preventing fires..
11. MS should establish a Pillar II Agroforestry Agri-Environment-Climate Measure (aka submeasure 10.1). This could be included in a Carbon Farming Scheme, which would meet the costs of soil carbon baselining, and subsequent monitoring, reporting and verification.
12. CAP Result Indicator 17 should read “Afforested and Agroforested Land: area in the farm “Reference Area” which is supported for afforestation, reforestation and agroforestation”. This is important since agroforested land remains as “agriculture” and should be recorded separately from afforestation.
13. Result Indicator 29 - Preserving Landscape Features - is a vital indicator and its removal by the AgFish Council should be reversed.
14. Result Indicators should be reported on annually and should include interventions funded outside the CAP - whose conditions are covered by “EU State Aid to Agriculture and Forestry Guidelines”.
15. All MS give their definition of “forest land” in the LULUCF Regulation. Small patches of tree-cover (e.g. <0.5ha in many countries) are not “forest” but are “Other Wooded Land” or “Other Land With Tree Cover” - using FAO definitions. Net GHG emissions from these areas should legally be reported in national inventories to the UNFCCC within the “grassland” or “cropland” categories. They are best considered as a component of agroforestry.